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Impact of Modern Guidance Information Systems in Socio-Economic Development: A Case Study of Huzhou City, China

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the key technology and implementation tools involved in the guidance information systems, outlines the operational processes, designs, and executes the relevant role. It emphasizes on the modern systems that are used in the social and economic development in recent times. This includes visual-purchase building of the guidance systems, being similar to the design of the space collection in the building environment, which plays an important role in guiding, instructing, and evacuating people. The key design methods of the guide system are defined from the point of view of the transmission of knowledge. From the various needs of visitors, the tourism management departments and the tourism related companies, and from the main to the branch, the tasks of the intelligent scenic spot information. This research idea is relevant to be applied in specific cases to provide tourists with a set of fast, convenient and practical tourism programs.

Keywords

Visual Guidance, Information Systems, Tourism, Communication, Design

Introduction

The development of technology is very fast in the field of visual designs and plays an important role to support human activities in both indoor and outdoor spaces in order to optimize time and increase safety. In the development of visual guidance information systems in the world of visual design is still on the rise recently for the guidance process of tourists, general populace across the world. According to psychological study, our visual and cognitive talents are critical in the navigating process (Bosch and Gharaveis 2017). This idea not only necessitates arduous labor and a significant time commitment, but it is also impossible to implement until the building is built. As a result, current studies propose forecasting tourists and passenger's way finding performance by assessing the quality of terminal's directional signage systems which is frequently done using a 3D perception approach. There are the other significant visual guidance aspects in the both outdoor and indoor spaces with respect to tourist's way finding process, aside from directional signage. Inside a passenger terminal, visual information can be split into two categories: valuable visual information and distracting visual

noise. What effect would adjacent visual noise (such as billboards and shop signs) have on user's visual cognition and navigation? The necessity to make pedestrian guidance systems measurable was previously confirmed (Bauer et al. 2018). Compared to other public buildings, the design of the circulation route in a passenger terminal and tourist's movement is much more complicated. The quality of transfer inside a passenger terminal and outdoor spaces imposes significant time and cost expenses on passengers (Guo and Wilson 2011). The efficiency of way finding is also crucial in evacuations during a fire or earthquake. Evacuees retrieve indications for their escape route from visual clues such as directional signage (Galea et al. 2017) and architectural spaces (Sun and de Vries 2006). To guide passengers to their destinations safely, efficiently and accurately in any situation, having an in-time, adequate and effective visual guidance system is of vital importance in a passenger terminal building

Figure 1: Effective visual information guidance systems at passenger terminal and buildings

Developments in technology and rapid urbanization cause growth in passenger numbers and building scales. Architects find it more and more difficult to use only their empirical knowledge to balance larger variations of design attributes. They often utilize computer analyses and simulations to help them predict the quality of their design work. This paper bridges the findings in visual cognitive psychology and computer vision with architectural design. It proposes a method that helps architects obtain a clearer understanding of the tourist's visual guidance quality during the design stages and when a passenger flow simulation cannot yet be performed. Architects can use this information to improve their design when necessary. Terminal management teams can also use this method to identify the problems that currently exist in the best-case scenario and optimize the guidance system's setup for safety and rapid emergency responses.

Materials and methods

The Elements of Visual Guidance Information Systems

In a passenger terminal, architectural space is the most important visual guidance element and the focus of architects. In people's way finding activities, symmetrical, regular, and continuous or well-ordered settings (Arthur and Passini, 1992) have been demonstrated to have beneficial guidance effects. The most effective

visual guiding is created by direct visual contact with the goal site. To analyze how architectural space assists people in navigating, Raubal, et al (1997) introduced the "image schemata." By questioning people about their spatial experiences while executing a way finding task, the approach was able to rebuild the built environment. According to surveys, 78 percent of interviewees believe that architectural design has an impact on their way finding performance (Foljanty, 2017). Parameters like visibility, view shed, and connectedness are frequently employed in the space syntax approach to assess "reachability" between two sites and estimate passenger way finding performance (Ueno, et al, 2009). This method employs a strictly geometric and quantitative approach to give a thorough examination of the links between various spaces. This method employs a strictly geometric and quantitative approach to give a thorough examination of the links between various spaces. Human visual and cognitive talents, on the other hand, are rarely regarded in this situation. Even though visibility between two locations is technically unobstructed, visual noise (such as marketing posters or even unusual architectural spaces) would almost certainly degrade navigation performance. Directional signage is an important visual aid that helps passengers find their way through an architectural area. These two visual guidance aspects work together very closely. It was discovered that when navigating was aided by appropriate signage and the building function was also well-designed, it appeared more natural certain researchers discovered that a decent signpost design could not compensate for the problems humans have while navigating inappropriately structured architectural spaces during way finding (Arthur and Passini, 1992). Not only did well-designed directional signage help to reduce the frequency of erroneous turns and requests for additional information, but it also helped to reduce feelings of crowding, discomfort, anger, and confusion (Wener and Kaminoff 1983).

There have been studies that look at directional signage as a separate source of visual guidance. A study was done to examine the relationship between signage conspicuity and illuminance in Swiss railway stations, and the ideal value was determined to be 100 cd/m² (Lasauskaite and Reisinger, 2015). There have also been studies that looked at directional signage and architectural areas combined. The impact of directional signage on passenger path choice behavior, for example, was investigated (Li and Xu 2019). The researchers rebuilt the path that the passenger was most likely to pick, and then the signage was adjusted using the Ant Colony Algorithm.

Figure 2: Illustrates directional signage as separate source of visual guidance

The visibility of signage was also evaluated using an agent-based simulation model (Nassar, 2011). Humans were modeled as intelligent agents moving in spaces with predefined patterns, and their perceptual attention was modeled taking into account their field of view as well as the signage location and design. The use of a landmark as a visual guide element can also make the navigation procedure more convenient. Landmarks serve as markers in the formation of a cognitive map within the human brain. Researchers looked at the participants' spoken travel instructions and sketch maps (Schwering et al, 2013).

Visual guiding elements are constantly in conflict with the surrounding visual noise, a characteristic that has been largely ignored by previous investigations. Distractions such as marketing posters and shop boards are continually striving to draw travelers away from the shortest path to destinations, whereas architectural spaces, directional signage, and landmarks intend to note the quickest path to destinations. Because visual noise cannot be defined and its content changes with each visual scene, quantifying (or even identifying) its impact is extremely challenging. The difficulty is that visual attention in humans must be replicated in order to understand how visual guiding elements and visual noise interact.

Effects of modern Visual Guidance Information Systems

Visual guidance information systems has become vital in global development be it in the social and economic growth of every country, it has the tendency to keep law and order in the society as well as optimize normal follow of operations, some of these are elaborated below.

Figure 3: Acquisition of information through purposeful designed audio-visual systems

Effective information through purposeful design method

With the rapid development of modern society and economy, the problem of information fragmentation is serious. People are not systematic in receiving information. People can focus more on effective information through purposeful design methods; Purposeful design takes a holistic look at all aspects of design including the people, the organization, and other key influences through a collaborative exchange of information. Designers' personal assumptions and perceptions for the final solutions are tempered by including valuable insights comprised of the users' needs, aspirations, and journeys within the design. This method ensures that the final design of the space feels as though it was created expressly for the people interacting within the environment.

Standardized business and social operations

Social production and business behavior need standardized operation, and too complex process will interfere with the people's correct implementation and guidance information system can address this very situation. Standardization can confer numerous competitive benefits to businesses, from the efficiencies gained in the manufacturing production line, to the massive, untapped productivity gains available to knowledge workers, to the implementation of cutting-edge performance-enhancing technologies such as robotics process automation (RPA), business intelligence (BI), advanced analytics, and customer-journey mapping for customer experience (CX) enhancement.

Figure 4: Visual guidance information system stabilize business and social operation

Maintain social order and standard human behavior

Modern visual guidance information systems can also make social order more perfect, maintain normal social life and production, and guide people's behavior so as to persuade people to be good subconsciously and make people's behavior more standardized at the moral level. Social order" to refer to a state of stability and consensus that exists in the absence of chaos and upheaval. People are influenced by the norms and beliefs of

their cultures and society. This influence can take a more personal and intimate level or a more general and widespread level that affects large numbers of people.

Figure 5: Social order and behavior standardized by visual guidance systems

The Role of Tourist Guide

The main role tourist guide is to escort groups or individual visitors from abroad or from the guiders own country around monuments, sites and museums of a city or region interpreting in a clear and entertaining way to inform the visitors about the culture and national heritage and environment. Guide provides full information about the features and history of the location. As the importance of places is known by the guide, the guide will educate and narrates you all the local stories, history and culture as and when the location comes.

The importance is placed on the guide's knowledge and will try to explain most of the concepts in a flexible language to the tourists. While traveling to next location, the guide entertains, and gives relevant information about the next place to be visited. On visiting any historical place, a guide with complete knowledge of that place is required to make the narration of the history regarding that place in detail. Moving without a guide will not come to know anything about the place and will not understand the main concept behind what is seen. A tour guide answers all questions to increase knowledge acquired from the tour. Many times it happens that several things are ignored especially things that are deemed irrelevant, but such things seen as small contains vital cultural and historical significance and can only revealed by the guide. Before going for a trip one can ask friends and relatives about the place who have been there. But to get the whole insight information it is better to appoint a guide.

Application of Modern Visual Guidance Information Systems in Tourism

With the development and changes of the society, people's lives are gradually exposed to more electronic products. The use of mobile phones and tablets facilitates their daily travel, especially during the travel process. Visitors can be provided with the best quality experience through the simple prompts of network

information, allowing them to purposely visit and play according to relevant orientation information. At present, tourism has used new media for publicity and planning. Its information can be obtained on the Internet and mobile APP. However, the lacking of systematic orientation design and tourism resource planning has led foreign tourists knowing a small amount of tourism resources and ignoring a large number of Human landscapes and scenic spots. Therefore, our innovation points are using the online and offline methods, using traditional and new media visual orientation design to improve the visual image guide system so that the tourists will be more standardized and systematic. The platform accommodates all aspects of the area, such as new publicity of attractions, new sightseeing routes, new visual orientation design and special services, new accommodations, etc., all these measures will better integrate and plan tourism resources, improve service functions, and build a service platform that facilitates and benefits to people.

Projections of the Application of modern visual Guidance Information System in Tourism

Today, with the rapid growth of globalization, culture's security and inheritance are emphasized throughout the world, demonstrating the prominent role of culture. If the product loses its cultural value, it will not be able to demonstrate its corresponding impact, so the marketing mechanism will be hindered and there will be no corresponding cultural consumption. There are various affluent communities of different ethnic groups and countries. The depth of the civilization of the region must be carried forward in the process of inheriting national culture. This is an important driving force for the diversified development of the new century. The promotion of regional culture is very important at this stage of tourism, and related regional cultural elements have become key elements in the design of the tourism visual information guidance and identification system. If the regional culture is not reflected in the design of the guidance system for tourism identification, it will not be able to display the identity of the entire tourism culture, so it has had a negative impact on tourists and has become a stumbling block to tourism growth. Via the application value of regional cultural elements in the design of tourism sign-oriented system, its future development trend is clearly showing on. "Let the five thousand-year civilization spread and help cater to "the development strategy of "going out" of the world by inheriting and carrying on the cultural elements with regional characteristics.

Figure 6: Visual information guidance systems with Cultural elements exhibited in tourism

It is the unavoidable outcome of the development of the period to a certain level, and it is also a sign of the success of the times. The cultural element in the future development of tourism Design of Humanized Traffic

Stations and Billboard Guidelines in Scenic Spots to provide tourism-oriented information, it is important to use visual guidance systems to set up billboards at high-speed intersections and service stations, high-speed rail stations, light rail stations and other transport points (food and accommodation maps). Increase the LED-oriented display system and mobile phone online inquiry at the same time in the scenic place, plan the tourist route reasonably and provide the best route guidance map.

On the basis of freely selecting the scenic spots, visitors can organize and monitor the time and set reminders and aid in locating the scenic spots and related services; scenic tour guides and staff can use unique uniform clothing that shows the Nanning landscape as a pattern of clothing, in the form of ink painting on the scenic clothing, accessories, enhance the characteristics of its scenic clothing The billboard establishment is intuitive and three-dimensional, which allows visitors to clarify what they need according to relevant guidelines, and to plan and have a purposeful tour. Through the design of different categories, they can make more targeted visits and appreciation. This is the most influential symbol of the use of the Area cultural elements.

Conclusion

Through the use of distinctive visual guidance in the tourist guide, in the process of serving scenic spots, it can completely meet the dual needs of visual aesthetics and spiritual culture of tourists, and display the special scenery and characteristics of the scenic location. By combining education with music, it can realize the construction of a harmonious tourism culture environment and help promote sustainable development of cultural resources in the region, create development channels for further development. Inheritance and development in scenic spots, promote the integration and advancement of tourism economy and scenic area culture. Every developed country in the world in recent times have organized and high-tech visual guidance information systems. Modern visual guidance information systems are therefore regarded as a tool to stabilize social and economic status being the core of every country and eventually, enhances the development of the country.

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